

Luminescent *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)] carboxylato complexes with non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs: Synthesis and mechanistic insights into the *in vitro* anticancer activity of *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)(aspirin)]

Joanna Skiba¹, Aleksandra Kowalczyk², Paweł Stączek², Tytus Bernaś³, Damian Trzybiński⁴, Krzysztof Woźniak⁴, Ulrich Schatzschneider⁵, Rafał Czerwieniec⁶ and Konrad Kowalski^{1,*}

¹Faculty of Chemistry, Department of Organic Chemistry, University of Łódź, Tamka 12, 91-403 Łódź, Poland

²Department of Microbial Genetics, Faculty of Biology and Environmental Protection, University of Łódź, Banacha 12/16, 90-237 Łódź, Poland

³Nencki Institute of Experimental Biology, Polish Academy of Sciences, ul. Pasteura 3, 02-093 Warszawa, Poland

⁴Faculty of Chemistry, Biological and Chemical Research Centre, University of Warsaw, Żwirki i Wigury 101, 02-089 Warszawa, Poland

⁵Institut für Anorganische Chemie, Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg, Am Hubland, D-97074 Würzburg, Germany

⁶Institut für Physikalische und Theoretische Chemie, Universität Regensburg, Universitätsstraße 31, D-93040 Regensburg, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Four *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)(L)] complexes with phen = 1,10-phenanthroline and L = non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) carboxylate ligand were obtained from the reaction of *fac*-[ReCl(CO)₃(phen)] with ligands such as aspirin, (*S*)-(+)-ibuprofen, (*S*)-(+)-naproxen and indomethacin, respectively. Single-crystal X-ray diffraction analysis revealed a pseudo-octahedral coordination of the rhenium atom whereas the NSAID carboxylates act as monodentate ligands. The complexes show orange-red luminescence in polar solvents. Of the four compounds obtained, only *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)(aspirin)] exhibited activity against HeLa human cancer cells while it was inactive against the non-tumorigenic mouse L929 cell line. After uptake and dissociation in HeLa cells, the *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)(aspirin)] complex produces the luminescent *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)]⁺ cation, which predominantly accumulates in the mitochondria but does not penetrate to the nucleus, as shown by confocal microscopy. Once generated, the *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)]⁺ cation reversibly binds to hen egg white lysozyme (HEWL) while the aspirin ligand holds the ability to inhibit the COX-2 enzyme. The anticancer activity of *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)(aspirin)] complex could be linked to ROS production, cell cycle disturbance what trigger apoptosis to occur.

INTRODUCTION

Inorganic and organometallic compounds have successfully entered the field of biology and medicinal sciences in many aspects.¹⁻¹⁵ Coordination of the metal center or a metal-containing fragment to a biomolecule very often allows for beneficial tuning of biological (*e.g.* anticancer or antibacterial) properties. Thus, metal-containing moieties have been

conjugated to a number of biological vectors including peptides,¹⁶ steroid hormones,¹⁷ nucleobases and nucleotides,^{18,19} and secondary natural products.²⁰ Synthetic drugs have also attracted great attention as targets for metal conjugation. Representative examples are half-sandwich iron-carbonyl derivatives of the antiepileptic drug 5,5-diphenylhydantoin,²¹ ferrocenyl and chromium carbonyl derivatives of the anthelmintic drugs monepantel²² and praziquantel,^{23,24} manganese carbonyl derivatives of antifungal drugs ketoconazole, miconazole, and clotrimazole,²⁵ ferrocenyl conjugates of vorinostat²⁶ and ferrocenyl analogues of the anticancer drug tamoxifen.²⁷

Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are a very important group of medications with anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antipyretic activity. Furthermore, acetylsalicylic acid (aspirin),²⁸ which is a key NSAID family member, shows antiplatelet^{29,30} and cancer prevention activity^{31,32} while naproxen reduces the risk of Alzheimer's disease^{33,34} and prevents bladder cancer progression.³⁵ Cyclooxygenases (COX-1 and COX-2) are molecular targets for NSAIDs.^{36,37} These enzymes catalyze the transformation of arachidonic acid into prostaglandins, which are mediators of inflammation and also involved in other biological processes such as angiogenesis.

The structures of NSAIDs are attractive scaffolds for chemical modifications. Relevant examples of metal-modified NSAID derivatives include Zn complexes of naproxen,³⁸ Cu complexes of salicylic acid^{39,40} and cobalt-alkyne derivatives of aspirin.⁴¹⁻⁴⁴ Depending on the metal center and the mode of its attachment to the NSAID core (direct coordination *vs.* conjugation *via* an appropriate linker), different profiles of biological activities have been observed. Accordingly, some Zn naproxen complexes show activity against certain *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strains³⁸ while square-planar bis-chelate Cu salicylic acid complexes serve as superoxide dismutase (SOD) mimetics and show cytotoxic activity against selected human cancer cells.⁴⁰ The mode of anticancer activity of these complexes

is not based on COX enzyme inhibition but instead it involves DNA binding and cleavage. In contrast, the anticancer activity of cobalt-alkyne derivatives of aspirin is explained by interference with COX-1 and COX-2 related metabolic pathways.^{41,42,44} In particular, it has been reported that some cobalt-alkyne aspirin derivatives acetylate the Lys-166, Lys-346, Lys-432 and Lys-598 lysine residues of COX-2.⁴² Furthermore, the same compound showed angiogenesis inhibitory activity in *Danio rerio* zebrafish embryos.⁴² This antiangiogenic activity effect has also been explained by COX enzymes inhibition.

Luminescent Re(I) complexes have attracted great attention as bioimaging probes and cytotoxic agents.⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸ Recently, we have directed our attention to Re(I) tricarbonyl diimine complexes of the general structure $fac-[Re(CO)_3(phen)(L)]$ with phen = 1,10-phenanthroline and L = carboxylate ligand.⁴⁹ This kind of compounds is generally known to display green to orange phosphorescence stemming from the metal-to-ligand charge-transfer (³MLCT) triplet excited state.^{49, 50-54} The emission occurs at a relatively long wavelength in the visible region and is characterized by microsecond decay times that allow for easy discrimination from the cell autofluorescence by time-gated microscopy. These two features favor $fac-[Re(CO)_3(phen)(L)]$ complexes as probes for biological applications. In particular, in a recent study, we demonstrated that $fac-[Re(CO)_3(phen)(L)]$ complexes with L = heptanoic acid, hept-6-ynoic acid, and 4-(1-ferrocenyl)-butanoic acid, dissociate inside living human HeLa cancer cells to produce the phosphorescent $fac-[Re(CO)_3(phen)]^+$ core.⁴⁹ This cation accumulates in the mitochondria of HeLa cells and increases the level of cellular reactive oxygen species (ROS).⁴⁹ Furthermore, it was shown that $fac-[Re(CO)_3(phen)]^+$ binds to the hen egg white lysozyme (HEWL) model protein.⁴⁹

Herein, we report on the synthesis, structure, luminescence and biological properties of $fac-[Re(CO)_3(phen)(L)]$ complexes with the ancillary ligand L being medicinally active NSAIDs: aspirin (**A**), (*S*)-(+)-ibuprofen (**B**), (*S*)-(+)-naproxen (**C**) and indomethacin (**D**;

Scheme 1). The goal of this study was to screen for antibacterial activity and get an insight in the mechanisms of anticancer activity of exemplary *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)(NSAID)] complex. Noticeably, the synthesis of some *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)(NSAID)] complexes has been published recently,⁵⁵ but the report lacks appropriate spectroscopic characterization for many of the compounds.

Results and Discussion

Synthesis

Compounds **1-4** were prepared by substitution⁴⁹ of the chlorido ligand in *fac*-[ReCl(CO)₃(phen)] with silver trifluoromethanesulfonate followed by reaction with the respective NSAID anions (Scheme 1).⁵⁴

Scheme 1 Synthesis of the *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)(NSAID)] complexes **1-4**

The reaction gave the products as yellow solids in 77% (**1**), 98% (**2**), 87% (**3**) and 95% (**4**) yield, respectively. The *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)(NSAID)] complexes are air-stable and can be stored for months without any signs of decomposition. Complexes **1-4** were characterized

by ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR and IR spectroscopy as well as EI mass spectrometry and elemental analysis. No ligand dissociation was observed by NMR spectroscopy in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) solution. In addition, aspirin complex **1** was dissolved in acetonitrile and studied by high-resolution ESI mass spectrometry. Three major sets of peaks were observed at 631.0510, 653.0310, and 1281.0702 Da, which are assigned to the cationic adducts $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$, $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ and the cluster ion $[2\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$, respectively (Figure S9). These results further confirm that the carboxylato ligand largely remains bound to the rhenium center even in strongly coordinating solvents, as there was only a weak signal for $[\text{Re}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})(\text{CO})_3(\text{phen})]^+$ at 492.0344 Da. The molecular structures of **1-3** were determined by single-crystal X-ray diffraction analysis. All analytical data confirmed the proposed composition. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of **1-4** are presented in Figure S1 to S8 of the Supporting Information. The IR spectra display three very strong $\nu_{(\text{C}=\text{O})}$ bands at 2019-1880 cm^{-1} and a strong $\nu_{(\text{C}=\text{O})}$ band at 1628-1620 cm^{-1} . Additional $\nu_{(\text{C}=\text{O})}$ bands at 1754 cm^{-1} and 1675 cm^{-1} are present in the IR spectra of complex **1** and **4**, respectively.

Single-Crystal X-ray Structural Analysis of Complexes 1-3

Crystals of **1** and **2** suitable for single-crystal X-ray diffraction analysis were grown from a mixture of DMSO and water, while crystals of **3** were obtained by slow diffusion of *n*-hexane into a saturated chloroform/methanol solution of **3**. The crystal and structure refinement data are presented in Table S1. Molecular structures of **1-3** are shown in Figs. 1-3 while selected geometrical parameters are listed in Table 1. Full list of bond distances (\AA), valence and torsion angles ($^\circ$) are listed in Table S2 to S10.

Fig. 1 Molecular structure of **1**. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity. Displacement ellipsoids are drawn at the 50% probability level.

Fig. 2 Molecular structure of **2**. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity. Displacement ellipsoids are drawn at the 50% probability level.

Fig. 3 Molecular structure of **3**. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity. Displacement ellipsoids are drawn at the 50% probability level.

Table 1 Selected bond lengths (Å), valence and torsion angles (°) for **1**, **2** and **3**

Parameter	Compound		
	1	2	3
Re1–C1	1.914(3)	1.986(9)	1.947(10)
Re1–C3	1.903(3)	1.923(7)	1.903(9)
Re1–O4	2.127(2)	2.152(5)	2.149(6)
Re1–N1	2.173(2)	2.194(6)	2.194(8)
C1–O1	1.147(4)	1.148(10)	1.125(11)
C3–O3	1.157(4)	1.151(9)	1.163(11)
O4–C16	1.292(3)	1.292(9)	1.289(11)
N1–Re1–N2	75.93(9)	76.0(2)	75.6(3)
C16–O4–Re1	126.06(17)	124.6(5)	122.9(6)
C3–Re1–O4	171.56(10)	173.1(3)	174.1(3)
N1–C4–C5–C6	-1.2(5)	0.1(12)	0.6(14)
N2–C14–C15–C7	-176.1(3)	177.7(6)	-178.2(8)
O5–C16–O4–Re1	4.2(4)	-0.9(11)	14.3(15)
O4–C16–C17–C18	-69.9(3)	-78.9(8)	-80.7(11)

The aspirin complex **1** crystallizes in the monoclinic space group $P2_1/n$ while compounds **2** and **3** crystallize in the orthorhombic space group $P2_12_12$, with one molecule of the given compound in the asymmetric unit of the crystal lattice. The single-crystal X-ray diffraction analysis of compounds **1–3** confirms the postulated structures in which the NSAID ligand is axially coordinated to the rhenium center. All three *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)(NSAID)] complexes exhibit a slightly distorted octahedral geometry, which is typical for this class of compounds.⁴⁹ The ibuprofen complex **2** and naproxen compound **3** have the expected (*S*)-configuration at the stereogenic carbon atom C17. The Re–O4 bond distances in **1**, **2** and **3** are 2.127(2), 2.152(5) and 2.149(6) Å, respectively. These are comparable to values reported in the literature.^{49,56} Some structural differences between the investigated compounds become apparent when comparing the orientation of the NSAID ligand relative to the phenanthroline ring system. In the case of complexes **1** and **3**, the absolute value of the dihedral angle between the aromatic ring plane of the NSAID ligand and that of the phenanthroline ligand is 57.4(1)° and 55.4(1)°, respectively (Fig. S9). In contrast, the plane of the phenyl ring of the ibuprofen ligand is much

more tilted relative to the plane of the phenanthroline ligand in complex **2**, with a dihedral angle of $66.5(1)^\circ$ (Fig. S9). These differences in the spatial orientation of the two molecular fragments in **1** and **3** vs. **2** is due to packing constraints in the crystal lattice.

Photophysical characterizations

The UV/Vis absorption spectra of *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)(NSAID)] complexes **1-4** are characterized by the presence of broad unstructured bands at 350–450 nm due to metal-to-ligand charge-transfer (MLCT) excitations and intense short wavelength phen intraligand absorptions at $\lambda_{\text{abs}} < 300$ nm. (Fig. 4 and Table 2). In the MLCT transitions, the electron density is shifted from the metal center to the phen ligand, as visualized in Fig. 5 for the lowest electronic transition of complex **1**. The compounds display moderately intense luminescence with a broad emission band centered at 640 nm when measured in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) at ambient temperature. This emission is assigned as phosphorescence from the lowest ³MLCT state.^{49-54,57} The decay times (in DMSO) are in the range of a few tens of nanoseconds in degassed solution. In aerated solutions, the decay times become slightly shorter due to quenching by molecular oxygen. Importantly, the quenching is not complete. Thus, the emission is easily detected both in oxygen-free samples and in solutions saturated with oxygen. In rigid media such as organic polymers, the emission maxima are blue shifted (spectra not shown) relative to liquid solutions and the decay times become significantly longer owing to suppressed excited-state geometry relaxations and slower nonradiative depopulation of the ³MLCT states. Therefore, *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)(NSAID)] complexes should be detectable in biological samples and the probe emission readily distinguished from cell autofluorescence, which occurs mostly in the blue spectral region.

Fig. 4 UV-Vis absorption (black line) and luminescence (red line) spectra of **1** in dimethyl sulfoxide at ambient temperature.

Table 2 Photophysical properties of Re complexes **1-4** determined in diluted dimethyl sulfoxide solutions at ambient temperature.

Compound	$\lambda_{\max, \text{abs}}^{\text{a}}$ (nm)	$\epsilon(\lambda_{\max, \text{abs}})^{\text{b}}$ ($\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$)	$\lambda_{\max, \text{em}}^{\text{c}}$ (nm)	τ_{degassed} (ns)	$\tau_{\text{nondegassed}}^{\text{e}}$ (ns)
1	365	$4.1 \cdot 10^3$	640	38	35
2	370	$3.7 \cdot 10^3$	640	29	26
3	365	$3.7 \cdot 10^3$	640	30	26
4	320^{f}	$9.6 \cdot 10^3^{\text{f}}$	640	33	31

a) Long wavelength band absorption maximum

b) Molar absorption coefficient at the maximum of the long wavelength band

c) Luminescence maximum

d) Luminescence decay time determined for degassed samples upon pulsed laser excitation at $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 378$ nm.

e) Luminescence decay time determined for air saturated samples upon pulsed laser excitation at $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 378$ nm.

f) The lowest energy MLCT band is partly overlapped with a higher energy absorption band of the axial ligand

Fig. 5 Contour plots of the frontier molecular orbitals of **1** as obtained for the electronic ground state geometry at the DFT B3LYP/def2-tzvp level of theory. TD-DFT calculations reveal the lowest electronic excitation (ground state \rightarrow $^3\text{MLCT}$) to be dominantly of HOMO \rightarrow LUMO character.

Biological studies

The antibacterial activity of the four title complexes was studied on Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* and Gram-negative *Escherichia coli* bacterial strains. Unfortunately, with exception for complex **1**, the title compounds dissolved poorly in the bacterial growth medium, which hindered antibacterial activity assays. Nonetheless, the antibacterial activity of the aspirin complex **1** was determined at concentrations up to 64 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, at which no precipitation occurred. Compound **1** exhibited antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* ATCC 6538 and ATCC 29213 and *E. coli* NCTC 8196 strains with a MIC value of 32 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. In comparison, the MIC values obtained for organic reference drugs ampicillin and nitrofurantoin against *S. aureus* ATCC 6538 and ATCC 29213 and *E. coli* NCTC 8196 strains were 1, 2 and 4 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for the former and 16, 16 and 8 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for the latter, respectively.

In addition, the anticancer activity of **1-4** complexes was investigated *in vitro* on HeLa human cervical epithelioid carcinoma cells and compared to non-tumorigenic mouse murine fibroblast L929 cells. IC_{50} values obtained with the tetrazolium (MTT) and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) assays are collected in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3. Effect of **1-4** and **A-D** on the viability of L929 and HeLa cells expressed as compound concentration inhibiting cell growth by 50% (IC₅₀; μ M). cisPt – cisplatin.

	IC ₅₀ [μ M]												
	24 h									72 h			
	1	2	3	4	A	B	C	D	cisPt	1	A	cisPt	
L929	109	12816	1022	1629	4245	5987	3387	839	26	-	-	-	
HeLa	36	371	306	158	2819	1006	13372	326	5	14	1669	1.2	

All ligands **A-D** are completely inactive under all conditions tested with IC₅₀ values larger than 300 μ M and in the micromolar range in many cases. Metal complexes **2-4** were also inactive as more than 150 μ M were required to inhibit cell growth by 50%. In contrast, the reference drug cisplatin had an IC₅₀ values of 5 μ M on HeLa cells under similar conditions. Only aspirin complex **1** displayed some promising activity, with an IC₅₀ values of 36 μ M at 24 h and 14 μ M after 72 h of incubation. Interestingly, HeLa cells were significantly more sensitive towards this compound than the L929 cells.

To determine whether the observed decrease in cell viability in the presence of **1** is due to cell lysis, a LDH assay was performed. As shown in Table 4, the amount of lysed cells detected upon exposure to complex **1** increased with concentration. At the highest concentration tested, complete membrane disruption was observed.

Table 4. Concentration depended lysis of L929 and HeLa cell lines upon exposure to **1** expressed as percentages of lysed cells detected by LDH leakage compared to totally lysed control (C 100%). Incubation time was 24 h.

Percentages of lysed cells [%]							
concentration [μ M]	12.5	25	50	100	200	400	C100%
L929	23	22	22	21	88	100	100
HeLa	26	28	36	72	99	102	100

Furthermore, there was a pronounced difference in the percentage of lysed cells when comparing the L929 and HeLa cell lines, as the latter showed a much higher degree of damaged cells at concentrations of 50 to 200 μ M under otherwise similar conditions.

In the next stage of the study, the induction of reactive oxygen species (ROS) production^{58,59} by metal complex **1** and ligand **A** was investigated in HeLa cells. The level of ROS was determined with the oxidation-sensitive dihydroethidium (DHE) fluorescent probe.⁶⁰ The probe easily penetrates through cellular membranes and allows detection of superoxide species.^{59,60} The amount of ROS was examined at $0.5\times IC_{50}$, IC_{50} and $2\times IC_{50}$ concentrations of **1** and **A**, respectively at 3 h treatment time (Fig. 6). Rhenium complex **1** generated higher amounts of ROS compared to the aspirin ligand at all concentrations tested. This effect is strongest at the $0.5\times IC_{50}$ concentration, where complex **1** produced 30% more ROS than aspirin. At the IC_{50} and $2\times IC_{50}$ concentrations, complex **1** generated approx. 45% more ROS than was detected in the control and approx. 25% more ROS than in aspirin treated cells. Thus, in the case of aspirin at higher concentrations, a 2-fold lower increase in ROS was observed compared to cells treated with **1**.

Fig 6. The relative ROS levels generated by **1** (grey) and **A** (white) in HeLa cells. The cells were incubated with concentrations of $0.5\times IC_{50}$, IC_{50} , $2\times IC_{50}$ for 3 h and then the level of ROS was determined with the cell-permeable fluorogenic probe dihydroethidium (DHE). The results represent mean \pm S.E.M. of data from 3 experiments. * $P < 0.05$ versus control

The luminescence properties of complex **1** were used to track it in bioimaging experiments. Accordingly, the subcellular distribution of **1** was investigated in living HeLa cells with confocal microscopy. Compound **1** was found in the interior of the cells after 1 h of incubation in a medium containing 1 μ M of the compound, which is well below cytotoxic concentrations. A fraction of **1** accumulated in the mitochondria, which is confirmed by the characteristic granular staining pattern (Fig 7A+B). In addition, diffuse emission was detected in the cytoplasm. This observation was verified by co-localization of **1** with the mitochondria-specific fluorescent probe MitoTracker Red® (Fig 7A) and quantified by determination of the Manders (MCC), Pearson (PCC) and Spearman correlation coefficient.⁶¹ Average values of Manders co-localization coefficients were 0.43 ± 0.15 (**1** with mitochondria, M1) and 0.71 ± 0.11 (mitochondria with **1**, M2). Likewise, average values of the Pearson and Spearman coefficients were 0.63 ± 0.19 and 0.76 ± 0.16 , respectively. This suggests that **1** accumulates not only in the mitochondria, but also in other subcellular compartments enclosed by lipid membranes, such as the Golgi apparatus and the endoplasmic reticulum. In contrast, complex **1** did not migrate into the nucleus of HeLa cells.

Fig. 7 Cellular distribution of **1** and mitochondrial staining. A) Luminescence of **1** (1 μ M, green) and MitoTracker Red® (red) in living HeLa cells and B) transmitted light image (gray). Scale bar – 10 μ m.

The molecular targets for NSAIDs are cyclooxygenases. Therefore, the COX-2 inhibition activity of complex **1** and aspirin was determined (Table 5).

Table 5. Concentration-dependent COX-2 inhibition [%] and IC₅₀ values [μM] of **1** and **A**. The results represent mean ± SEM, n=3, * P < 0.001 **A** versus **1**.

COX-2 Inhibition [%]					
concentration [μM]	10	50	100	500	IC ₅₀ [μM]
A	3.3±2.5	13.2±0.2	17.7±4.1	22.4±1.1 *	1250
1	13.2±0.8 *	14.4±1.8	20.3±3.1	46.1±5.6 *	696

In the 10 to 100 μM concentration range, **1** and **A** show a comparable inhibitory activity. Only at high concentrations, complex **1** showed a ~2.0 times stronger inhibitory effect compared to aspirin. This difference is extremely significant ($P < 0.001$), but only occurs at a concentration of 500 μM. It is hypothesized that at higher concentration, **1** binds to the protein in a non-specific mode (not only in the active site) and that this binding also inhibits enzyme activity. To obtain further insight in the protein binding ability of complex **1**, it was incubated in pure water with hen egg white lysozyme (HEWL) serving as a model protein and the solution subjected to ESI mass spectrometry. At short incubation time, the spectrum shows the prominent peak of $[M+Na]^+$ at 653.0321 Da together with the signals of the +7H to +12H protonation states of the lysozyme (Fig. S11). The most abundant peak is due to the $[lysozyme+9H]^{9+}$ species, with the isotope distribution centered at around 1590.4 Da. There are also two weak additional peaks at 1660.1 and 1664.4 Da. Based on the mass differences, these can be assigned to $[lysozyme+9H+1]^{9+}$ and possibly $[lysozyme+9H+1+2H_2O]^{9+}$, but the signal disappeared when the sample is remeasured after 20 h, indicating that the interaction of the metal complex with the protein is only weak and the rhenium complex undergoes further speciation at extended incubation time leading to unassigned follow-up products.

Inhibition of the cell cycle in cancer cells is often a key mechanism of action of anticancer agents. Therefore, a cell cycle analysis was carried out in HeLa cells incubated for 24 h with IC₅₀ concentration of the complex **1** or **A** and analyzed by the flow cytometry with propidium iodide (PI) staining. DNA histograms obtained from the cytometric analysis showed profound disturbances in the cell cycle of HeLa cells (Fig. 8, Table 6).

Fig. 8 Histograms of the cell cycle distribution in HeLa cells treated with IC₅₀ concentrations of **1** and **A**.

Table 6. Cell cycle distribution of HeLa cells treated with IC₅₀ concentrations of **1** and **A** for 24 h. Percentage of DNA in a particular phase of the cell cycle was calculated from the DNA histograms using FlowJo 7.6.1 software.

	Cell cycle distribution [% of cells]			
	sub-G1	G0/G1	S	G2/M
Control	2.7	48.3	34.2	14.1
A	5.0	45.1	30.1	21.6
1	13.7	21.6	51.8	15.4

Complex **1** caused approx. 14% of the cells arrested in the sub-G1 phase, which is a sign of pro-apoptotic activity. At the same time, a decrease of cells in the G0/G1 phase was observed, which was accompanied by an almost 18% increase of cells in the S phase and slight G2/M cell arrest when compared to control cells. The S phase arrest may indicate that some vital resources were depleted in cells exposed to **1**. The alterations in the cell cycle distribution caused by

aspirin (**A**) were not such significant but the compound also causes a slight increase of sub-G1 cells (2% vs. control at IC₅₀ concentration of 2819 μ M).

The appearance of cells in the sub-G1 phase and increased ROS levels after treatment with **1** prompted us to investigate apoptosis as possible mechanism of cell death, which was verified by the Annexin V and Caspase-3/7 assays (Fig. 10). The Annexin V assay measures the real-time exposure of phosphatidylserine (PS) on the outer leaflet of cell membranes during the apoptotic process. Specific proteins which are components of the assay kit bind to PS and generate a chemoluminescence signal. Furthermore, a second dye which is a fluorescent upon DNA binding, stains cells which have lost membrane integrity. Thus, the Annexin V assay enables discrimination between apoptotic and necrotic cells. Caspases 3 and 7 are effector caspases that act on a variety of substrates (*e.g.* DNA) to induce the final stages of apoptosis.

Fig 10. Determination of mechanism of cell death induced by compound **1**. (**A**) HeLa cells were treated with IC₅₀ and chemiluminescence (green) and fluorescence (red) were measured over 24 hours. The increase of emission corresponds to the exposure of phosphatidylserine (PS) on the outer leaflet of the cell membrane while the increase of emission corresponds to the loss of membrane integrity. For IC₅₀ concentration of **1** there is a significant time delay between the emergence of PS: Annexin V binding and the loss of membrane integrity, results that are indicative of an apoptotic phenotype leading to secondary necrosis. Data represent the mean of 3 experiments. (**B**) The caspase 3/7 activity induced by compound **1** in HeLa cells. The cells were incubated with concentration of 1/2 IC₅₀, IC₅₀, 2 x IC₅₀ of **1** for 6 h and then the caspase activity was measured. The results represent mean \pm S.E.M. of data from 3 experiments. *P < 0.05 versus control.

The results obtained with the Annexin V assay showed that already in the first hours after the addition of compound **1**, the cell membrane was reorganized and phosphatidylserine (PS) appears on the outer leaflet of the cell membrane with a slight disintegration of membrane, suggesting the induction of apoptosis by compound **1**. The caspase 3/7 assay further substantiated the pro-apoptotic activity of **1**, as the rhenium complex increased expression of caspase 3/7 in a dose-dependent manner (Fig. 10). At $0.5 \times IC_{50}$, a slight 4% activation was observed while at IC_{50} and $2 \times IC_{50}$ concentrations, the expression increased to 26 and 152% over control, respectively. On the basis of the above results, apoptosis induction by **1** in HeLa cells appears to be quite pronounced.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, four *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)(L)] complexes with L = aspirin, ibuprofen, naproxen, and indomethacin were synthesized and characterized. The compounds display a orange-red phosphorescence from the lowest ³MLCT state of the *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)]⁺ core. While antimicrobial activity studies were hampered by insufficient solubility in growth medium, anticancer activity studies in human cancerous HeLa cells showed *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)(aspirin)] as the most active complex. As indicated by an IC_{50} value of 36 μ M, these cells were more sensitive to the complex than the non-tumorigenic F929 cells (IC_{50} = 109 μ M). Confocal microscopy revealed predominant accumulation of the *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)]⁺ cation in the mitochondria, but negligible localization in the nucleus. Furthermore, complex **1** also induced increased ROS levels in HeLa cells and has a substantial influence on the cell cycle, increasing cells in the Sub-G1 and S phases. All these features indicate a pro-apoptotic mode of action of the *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)(aspirin)] complex in HeLa cells. In addition, the complex showed COX-2 inhibitory activity as well as non-specific binding to lysozyme, as indicated by ESI-MS analysis. This feature supports a dissociation-driven mechanism of cellular action. In summary, *fac*-

[Re(CO)₃(phen)(aspirin)] displays a mode of action determined by its two components, the COX-2 inhibitory activity characteristic of the aspirin ligand and the apoptosis induction activity triggered by mitochondrial accumulation of the *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)]⁺ cation.

Experimental

General methods

All preparations were carried out using standard Schlenk techniques. Chromatographic separations used aluminium oxide (EcoChromTM MP Biomedicals). Tetrahydrofuran was distilled and purged with argon prior to use. Other solvents were of reagent grade and used without prior purification. Aspirin, (*S*)-(+)-ibuprofen, (*S*)-(+)-naproxen and indomethacin were purchased from commercial suppliers and used without further purification. ¹H NMR (600 MHz) and ¹³C{¹H} NMR (150 MHz) spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance III 600 spectrometer operating at 298 K. Chemical shifts are reported in δ units (ppm) using the residual signal of DMSO (¹H δ 2.50 ppm, ¹³C δ 39.70) as the reference. EI mass spectra were recorded on a Finnigan MAT 95 mass spectrometer. Electrospray mass spectra were obtained on a ThermoFisher Exactive Plus instrument with an Orbitrap mass analyser in positive ion mode at a resolution of $R = 70.000$ and a solvent flow rate of 10 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ using acetonitrile as the solvent. For the protein interaction study, water was used as the solvent and the flow rate increased to 100 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$. Only the most intense peak of each isotope pattern is reported. IR spectra (KBr pellets) were measured on a FTIR Nexus Nicolet apparatus. Microanalyses were carried out by the Analytical Services of the Polish Academy of the Sciences (Łódź).

Synthesis

General procedures for synthesis of *fac*-[Re(CO)₃(phen)(L)] with phen = 1,10-phenanthroline and L = aspirin, (*S*)-(+)-ibuprofen, (*S*)-(+)-naproxen and indomethacin complexes **1-4** are given below.

The appropriate ligand **A-D** (0.16 mmol) and *fac*-[ReCl(CO)₃(phen)] (80 mg, 0.16 mmol) were dissolved in anhydrous degassed tetrahydrofuran (30 mL). The reaction mixture was stirred for 5 min, then trimethylamine (33 μ L, 24 mg, 0.24 mmol) and silver trifluoromethanesulfonate (49 mg, 0.19 mmol) were added and the mixture stirred at 70 °C for 18 h. The solvent was evaporated to dryness and the residue subjected to column chromatography on deactivated alumina (30 g Al₂O₃ and 1.25 mL water) with dichloromethane as the eluent. Analytically pure products were obtained after recrystallization from dichloromethane/*n*-hexane mixtures. Compound **1**, yellow solid, yield: (79 mg, 77 %); **2**, yellow solid, yield: (105 mg, 98 %); **3**, yellow solid, yield: (95 mg, 87 %); **4**, yellow solid, yield: (123 mg, 95 %).

1: ¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ = 9.51 (dd, 2H, $J_{\text{HH}} = 4.8$ Hz, $J_{\text{HH}} = 1.2$ Hz, phen), 8.95 (dd, 2H, $J_{\text{HH}} = 8.4$ Hz, $J_{\text{HH}} = 1.2$ Hz, phen), 8.28 (s, 2H, phen), 8.12 (dd, 2H, $J_{\text{HH}} = 8.4$ Hz, $J_{\text{H,H}} = 4.8$ Hz, phen), 7.15 (dt, 1H, $J_{\text{HH}} = 7.5$ Hz, $J_{\text{HH}} = 1.8$ Hz, C₆H₄), 6.82 (dt, 1H, $J_{\text{HH}} = 7.5$ Hz, $J_{\text{HH}} = 1.8$ Hz, C₆H₄), 6.75 (dt, $J_{\text{HH}} = 7.8$ Hz, 1.8 Hz, 2H, C₆H₄), 1.92 (s, 3H, CH₃). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (150 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ = 198.2, 194.3, 168.4, 168.3, 154.2, 148.8, 146.0, 139.6, 130.5, 130.4, 130.2, 129.2, 127.7, 126.4, 124.9, 122.7, 20.8. EI-MS: m/z = 630 [M]⁺, 602 [M-CO]⁺, 546 [M-3CO]⁺. ESI-MS (CH₃CN): 631.0494 [M+H]⁺, 653.0310 [M+Na]⁺, 1281.0702 [2M+Na]⁺. FTIR (KBr v [cm⁻¹]): 3056, 3060, 2015 (C=O), 1902 (C≡O), 1884 (C≡O), 1754 (C=O), 1628 (C=O), 1429, 1355, 1196, 850, 725. Anal. Calcd for C₂₄H₁₅N₂O₇Re (%): C 45.78, H 2.40, N 4.45; Found: C 45.86, H 2.52, N 4.50.

2: ¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ = 9.35 (dd, 1H, $J_{\text{HH}} = 5.4$ Hz, $J_{\text{HH}} = 1.2$ Hz, phen), 9.33 (dd, 1H, $J_{\text{HH}} = 5.4$ Hz, $J_{\text{HH}} = 1.2$ Hz, phen), 8.90 (dd, 1H, $J_{\text{HH}} = 7.0$ Hz, $J_{\text{HH}} = 1.2$ Hz, phen), 8.88 (dd, 1H, $J_{\text{HH}} = 7.0$ Hz, $J_{\text{HH}} = 1.2$ Hz, phen), 8.24 (s, 2H, phen), 8.02 (m, 2H, phen), 6.38 (pseudo-d, 2H, $J_{\text{HH}} = 7.8$ Hz, C₆H₄), 6.04 (pseudo-d, 2H, $J_{\text{HH}} = 7.8$ Hz, C₆H₄), 2.84 (q, 1H, $J_{\text{HH}} = 6.6$ Hz, *CH), 2.24 (d, 2H, $J_{\text{HH}} = 7.2$ Hz, CH₂), 1.66 (m, 1H, CH), 0.79 (d, 3H, $J_{\text{HH}} = 4.8$ Hz,

CH_3), 0.78 (d, 3H, $J_{HH} = 4.2$ Hz, CH_3), 0.65 (d, 3H, $J_{HH} = 6.6$ Hz, CH_3). $^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR (150 MHz, DMSO- d_6): $\delta = 198.5, 177.0, 153.9, 153.7, 146.0, 145.9, 140.5, 139.3, 139.2, 137.7, 130.4, 130.3, 127.8, 127.7, 127.5, 126.2, 126.0, 125.8, 46.1, 44.3, 29.6, 22.33, 22.31, 19.1$. EI-MS: $m/z = 611 [M-CO_2]^+$, 451 $[C_{15}H_8N_2O_3Re]^+$. FTIR (KBr $\nu [cm^{-1}]$): 3084, 3061, 2966, 2928, 1892, 2017 (C \equiv O), 1900 (C \equiv O), 1880 (C \equiv O), 1620 (C=O), 1429, 1375, 1362, 853, 725. Anal. Calcd for $C_{28}H_{25}N_2O_5Re$ (%): C 51.29, H 3.84, N 4.27; Found: C 51.17, H 3.92, N 4.31.

3: 1H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO- d_6): $\delta = 9.32$ (dd, 1H, $J_{HH} = 5.4$ Hz, $J_{HH} = 1.2$ Hz, phen), 9.23 (dd, 1H, $J_{HH} = 5.4$ Hz, $J_{HH} = 1.2$ Hz, phen), 8.76 (dd, 1H, $J_{HH} = 8.4$ Hz, $J_{HH} = 1.2$ Hz, phen), 8.58 (dd, 1H, $J_{HH} = 8.4$ Hz, $J_{HH} = 1.2$ Hz, phen), 7.97 (dd, 1H, $J_{HH} = 9.6$ Hz, $J_{HH} = 5.4$ Hz, phen), 7.95 (d, 1H, $J_{HH} = 9.0$ Hz, phen), 7.87 (d, 1H, $J_{HH} = 9.0$ Hz, phen), 7.86 (pt, 1H, $J_{HH} = 3$ Hz, phen), 7.28 (d, 1H, $J_{HH} = 9.0$ Hz, $C_{10}H_6$), 7.06 (m, 2H, $C_{10}H_6$), 6.95 (d, 1H, $J_{HH} = 8.4$ Hz, $C_{10}H_6$), 6.68 (s, 1H, $C_{10}H_6$), 6.19 (dd, 1H, $J_{HH} = 8.7$ Hz, $J_{HH} = 1.2$ Hz, $C_{10}H_6$), 3.92 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 2.99 (q, 1H, $J_{HH} = 7.2$ Hz, *CH), 0.80 (d, 3H, $J_{HH} = 7.2$ Hz, CH_3). $^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR (150 MHz, DMSO- d_6): $\delta = 198.4, 176.9, 156.7, 153.6, 153.5, 145.6, 145.5, 139.1, 139.0, 138.4, 132.2, 130.1, 130.0, 128.9, 127.8, 127.3, 127.1, 126.0, 125.7, 125.5, 125.4, 123.9, 118.0, 105.8, 55.3, 46.3, 18.5$. EI-MS: $m/z = 636 [M-CO_2]^+$, 451 $[C_{15}H_8N_2O_3Re]^+$. FTIR (KBr $\nu [cm^{-1}]$): 3068, 3025, 2966, 2930, 2868, 2019 (C \equiv O), 1918 (C \equiv O), 1886 (C \equiv O), 1620 (C=O), 1604, 1427, 1340, 858, 726. Anal. Calcd for $C_{29}H_{21}N_2O_6Re$ (%): C 51.25, H 3.11, N 4.12;. Found: C 51.29, H 3.26, N, 4.18.

4: 1H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO- d_6): $\delta = 9.20$ (dd, $J_{HH} = 4.8$ Hz, 1.2 Hz, 2H, phen), 8.62 (dd, $J_{HH} = 8.1$ Hz, 1.2 Hz, 2H, phen), 7.94 (s, 2H, phen), 7.85 (dd, $J_{HH} = 8.1$ Hz, 4.8 Hz, 2H, phen), 7.63 (pseudo-d, $J_{HH} = 8.4$ Hz, 2H, C_6H_4), 7.58 (pseudo-d, $J_{HH} = 8.4$ Hz, 2H, C_6H_4), 6.64 (d, $J_{HH} = 9.0$ Hz, 1H, C_6H_3), 6.51 (dd, $J_{HH} = 9.0$ Hz, 2.4 Hz, 1H, C_6H_3), 6.13 (d, $J_{HH} = 2.4$ Hz, 1H, C_6H_3), 3.63 (s, 3H, CH_3O), 2.86 (s, 2H, CH_2), 1.34 (s, 3H, CH_3). $^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR (150 MHz, DMSO- d_6): $\delta = 198.4, 194.6, 173.4, 167.1, 154.9, 153.2, 145.4, 139.1, 137.2, 134.6, 132.7, 130.8,$

130.4, 129.7, 129.3, 129.0, 127.1, 125.4, 115.9, 114.4, 110.7, 100.8, 55.1, 32.1, 12.4. EI-MS: $m/z = 763$ $[M-CO_2]^+$, 451 $[C_{15}H_8N_2O_3Re]^+$. FTIR (KBr v $[cm^{-1}]$): 3066, 2927, 2833, 2017 (C≡O), 1908 (C≡O), 1886 (C≡O), 1675 (C=O), 1624 (C=O), 1476, 1428, 1326, 1225, 842. Anal. Calcd for $C_{34}H_{23}N_3O_7ClRe$ (%): C 50.59, H 2.87, N 5.21; Found: C 50.61, H 2.95, N 5.24.

X-ray structure analysis

Good quality single-crystals of **1–3** were selected for the X-ray diffraction experiments at $T = 100(2)$ K. They were mounted with paratone-N oil on MiTeGen micro-mounts. Diffraction data was collected on Agilent Technologies SuperNova Single Source (**1** and **2**) and Dual Source (**3**) diffractometers with $MoK\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073$ Å) (**1** and **2**) and $CuK\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54184$ Å) using CrysAlis RED software.⁶² In all cases, the analytical numerical absorption correction using a multifaceted crystal model based on expressions derived by R.C. Clark & J.S. Reid⁶³ as implemented in the SCALE3 ABSPACK scaling algorithm were applied (CrysAlis CCD and CrysAlis RED, Oxford Diffraction, Oxford Diffraction Ltd: Yarnton, 2008.). Structural determinations were carried out using SHELX.⁶⁴ The structures were solved with direct methods and then successive least-square refinement was carried out based on the full-matrix least-squares method on F^2 using the SHELXL program.⁶⁴ All H atoms were positioned geometrically, with C–H equal to 0.93, 0.96, 0.97 and 0.98 Å for the aromatic, methyl, methylene and methane H-atoms, respectively, and constrained to ride on their parent atoms with $U_{iso}(H) = xU_{eq}(C)$, where $x = 1.2$ for the aromatic, methylene and methine H-atoms, and $x = 1.5$ for the methyl H-atoms. In case of **1** and **2** the acetate and isobutyl moieties of the carboxylic ligand are disordered over two positions with occupancy of 84 : 16% and 69 : 31% for **1** and **2**, respectively. In case of **3**, few distinct peaks on the difference Fourier map are indicating the presence of a disordered solvent molecule. All attempts to model a disordered

solvents used for crystallization failed. Therefore, the solvent contribution has been removed applying the appropriate MASK procedure in Olex2 program.⁶⁵ Calculated solvent accessible volume was approximately 404.1 Å³ occupied by 115.0 electrons per unit cell. In case of **1** the atoms of disordered part of the molecule were subject to numerous SADI and ISOR restraints. In **3** the ISOR restraints were applied to the atoms O2, C3, C14–C16 and C29, while in **2** to the atom O2. The figures for this publication were prepared using Olex2 program.⁶⁴

CCDC 1867809 (**1**), 1867810 (**2**) and 1867811 (**3**) contain the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. The data can be obtained free of charge from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/structures.

Spectrophotometric and spectrofluorimetric measurements

UV/Vis absorption spectra were recorded with a Varian Cary 300 double beam spectrometer. Luminescence and excitation spectra were measured with a Horiba Jobin Yvon Fluorolog 3 steady-state fluorescence spectrometer. For decay time measurements a PicoQuant LDH-P-C-375 pulsed diode laser ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 372$ nm, pulse width 100 ps) was applied as the excitation source. The emission signal was detected with a cooled photomultiplier attached to a FAST ComTec multichannel scalar card with a time resolution of 250 ps. Molecular and electronic structures were computed using the density functional theory (DFT) and time-dependent density functional theory (TDDFT) with the hybrid gradient corrected correlation functional B3LYP⁶⁶ and split-valence def2-tzvp basis set with a relativistic effective core potential for inner core rhenium electrons.⁶⁷ All calculations were performed using the NWChem software.⁶⁸

Confocal microscopy

Human HeLa 21.4 cells were cultured for 48 h after seeding in Petri dishes with glass bottom (MaTek), reaching approximately 50% confluency. The cells were grown in Dulbecco's minimal essential medium (DMEM) with 5% FCS, at 5% CO₂ and 37°C. The same medium was used to perform all microscopy experiments. Before imaging the cells were preincubated

for 1 h with 1 μ M, added to the imaging medium. Stock solutions of the compound (1 mM) were freshly prepared in DMSO (500 μ M). Mitochondria of live cells were labelled (where indicated) with MitoTracker® Red (Thermofisher, Poland) by incubation with 100 nM of the dye for 20 minutes following incubation with **1**. Imaging was performed using Leica SP8 confocal system, equipped with a DMI6000 inverted microscope, 63 \times oil immersion objective (NA 1.4), 405 nm pulsed (40 MHz) diode laser (5 mW nominal power), 1500 mW supercontinuum laser (WLL), hybrid (HyD) and conventional (PMT) detectors. Luminescence of **1** was excited using the 405 laser (5%) and registered (HyD, integration mode) from single confocal sections (pinhole set to 1 Airy unit) in 500 – 560 nm range. Fluorescence of MitoTracker Red was excited with 580 nm light (WLL, 0.5%) and detected in 585 – 650 nm range with PMT. The luminescence and transmitted light images were collected with the speed of 100 lines/s and pixel size of 0.09 μ m. Co-localization was quantified with ImageJ (Coloc 2 plugin).

Biology

Antibacterial assay

The *in vitro* antimicrobial activity of **1-4** was evaluated against the reference strains of Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli* NCTC 8196, *Proteus vulgaris* ATCC 49990, *Proteus mirabilis* ATCC 29906, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* NCTC 6749), and Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 29213, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* ATCC 12228) bacterial species. The minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined as the lowest concentration of the compound preventing growth of the tested microorganism using microdilution method according to EUCAST guidelines ISO 20776-1 (2006). The 96-well microplates were used; 50 μ l of recommended Mueller–Hinton broth with a series of twofold dilutions of the tested compound in the range of the final concentrations from 4 to 256 μ g/mL was inoculated with 50 μ l of microbial suspension with a final bacterial cell number

concentration approximately 5×10^5 CFU/mL. All of the tested compounds were dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and its final concentration on plate (2%) had no influence on growth of microorganisms. The incubation was carried out at 37°C for 18 h and optical density (OD₆₀₀) was measured. Ampicillin and streptomycin were used as control antimicrobials. All evaluations were performed in triplicates.

Cell culture

Murine fibroblasts L929 cells (ATTC® - CCL-1, mouse fibroblasts) and human tumor HeLa cells (ATTC® - CCL-2™, human epithelial cells) were obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, Rock-ville, USA) and used for cell viability assay. HeLa cells were used then for LDH release assay, oxidative stress response, comet assay and cytometric measurement of cell cycle distribution. Both adherent cell lines were cultured as a monolayer in IMDM medium supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), 100 U/mL of penicillin and 100 µg/mL of streptomycin. The cell cultures were incubated at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 10% CO₂. The growth medium was changed 2 times per week and the cells were subcultured every 5 days in order to maintain them in the exponential growth phase.

Cell viability assay

The effect of compounds **1-4** and their respective NSAID on host cells was detected by determining cellular viability using MTT reduction assay. L929 and HeLa cells were plated in 96-well microplates at density of 1×10^4 cells per well. After overnight incubation tested compounds were added in twofold dilutions from 10 to 400 µM. All of the tested compounds were dissolved in DMSO and its final concentration on plate (1%) had no influence on cells viability. Cisplatin dissolved in 150 mM saline was used as known, toxic, antitumor agent. After 24 h incubation MTT (3-(4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-Diphenyltetrazolium Bromide) at concentration of 0.5 mg/mL was added and plates were incubated for the next 2 h at 37°C, 10% CO₂. Then, formazan crystals were solubilized in 150 µl DMSO and the optical density was

measured at 550 nm. The results of the experiments were shown as mean arithmetic values from 3 repeats in each of two independent experiments and the percentage of viability inhibition in comparison to untreated control was calculated for each concentration of the tested compounds and IC₅₀ values were determined with Prism GraphPad 7 software using nonlinear curve fitting to the dose–response curve.

Cytotoxicity assay

The cytotoxic effect on L929 and HeLa cells of compound **1** was measured by lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) release in colorimetric reaction (Promega, CytoTox 96® Non-Radioactive Cytotoxicity Assay). LDH is a stable cytosolic enzyme that is released upon cell lysis, and can be used to measure membrane integrity. L929 or HeLa cells were plated in 96-well microplates at density of 1×10^4 cells per well. After overnight incubation compound **1** was added in twofold dilutions from 12.5 to 400 μ M. All of the tested compounds were dissolved in DMSO and its final concentration on plate (1%) had no influence on cells viability. After 18 h incubation with compound, 50 μ L aliquots from each wells were transferred to a fresh 96-well plate, 50 μ L of the CytoTox 96R reagent was added and incubated for 30 min at room temperature in dark. The Stop solution was then added and the absorbance at 490 nm was measured. The results of the experiments were shown as mean arithmetic values from three repeats in each of two independent experiments and the percentage of tested compound cytotoxicity in comparison to maximum LDH release control, treated with lysis solution for 45 minutes before experiment, was calculated for each concentration.

Oxidative stress

The intracellular level of reactive oxygen species (ROS) was determined on the basis of oxidative conversion of non-fluorescent dihydroethidium (hydroethidine or DHE) by superoxide to form fluorescent 2-hydroxyethidium or by non-specific oxidation by other sources of reactive oxygen species (ROS) to form ethidium. The HeLa cells were seeded in

complete IMDM medium with 10% FBS at the density of 2×10^4 cells/well onto black 96-well microculture plate. After overnight incubation the cells were incubated for 3 hours with compound **1** or **A** at concentration $1/2 IC_{50}$, IC_{50} and $2 \times IC_{50}$. Then the plate was centrifuged 5 minutes, 1600 rpm, medium above cell was carefully aspirated and 200 μ L of 5 mM DHE was added. The plate was incubated for 20 minutes at 37°C protected from light. After incubation the cells monolayer was washed twice with phosphate buffered saline (PBS) and the fluorescence was measured using an excitation wavelength 535 nm and emission 635 nm. All evaluations were performed in triplicates. An one way ANOVA analysis of variance with a Tukey post hoc was used for multiple comparisons. All statistics were calculated with Prism GraphPad 7 software. A P value of <0.05 was considered significant.

Cox-2 inhibition assay

The cyclooxygenase isoenzyme 2 (COX-2) inhibition by compound **1** was measured using COX-2 Inhibitor Screening Kit (BioVision). The assay is based on the fluorometric detection of Prostaglandin G₂, the intermediate product generated by the COX enzyme. The method was based on the protocol supplied by the manufacturer. In short, 80 μ L of reaction master mix (76 μ L COX assay buffer, 1 μ L COX probe, 2 μ L diluted COX cofactor, 1 μ L COX-2 enzyme) was added on white 96-well plate with flat bottom. Then 10 μ L of compound **1** at concentrations from 10 to 500 μ M was added and incubated for 10 min on ice. For the inhibitor control we used Celecoxib as a known COX-2 inhibitor and for the enzyme control the assay buffer was added instead of the inhibitor. Additionally, DMSO at proper concentration was checked for solvent effect on enzymatic activity. To initiate the reaction 10 μ L of diluted Arachidonic Acid/NaOH solution was added into each well and fluorescence (Ex/Em = 535/587 nm) was measured kinetically at 25°C for 5 min. All evaluations were performed in triplicates. A two way ANOVA analysis of variance with a Bonferroni post-tests were used for multiple

comparisons. All statistics were calculated with Prism GraphPad 7 software. A P value of <0.05 was considered significant.

Cytometric measurement of cell cycle distribution

The cell cycle distribution was analyzed using propidium iodide staining and flow cytometry measurement. Briefly, 100 000 exponentially growing HeLa cells were seeded on a 6-well plate in 2 mL of a complete culture medium per well and were allowed to attach for 24 h. Then the compound **1** or aspirin was added at concentration of IC₅₀ and the plate was incubated for another 24 h. Untreated cells were used as a control. The cells were then harvested by trypsinization, suspended in 1 mL of culture medium, centrifuged at 400×g for 10' and washed twice with PBS. The cell sediment was re-suspended in PBS and adjusted to the density of approx. 1×10⁶/mL and fixed in 70% ice-cold ethanol. After storing the cells for at least 10 h at 4°C they were stained in 200 µL of propidium iodide staining solution (75 µM propidium iodide and 50 Kunitz units per mL of RNase A in PBS) and incubated for 30 min at 37°C in darkness. The cell cycle distribution was analyzed by flow cytometry using LSRII (Becton Dickinson).⁶⁹ instrument at 488 nm excitation and 575/26 emission wavelengths and the cell cycle phase distribution was determined with FlowJo 7.6.1 software (FlowJo, LLC) using a built-in cell cycle analysis module (Watson pragmatic algorithm).

Apoptosis and necrosis determination

The induction of apoptosis or necrosis in HeLa cells treated with compound **1** and **a** was measured by using the RealTime-Glo Annexin V Apoptosis and Necrosis Assay (Promega). It is a live-cell (non-lytic) real-time assay that measures the exposure of phosphatidylserine on outer leaflet of the cell membrane which is an early indicator of apoptosis. Simultaneously necrosis was detected by cell-impermeant, profluorescent DNA dye. The method was based on the protocol supplied by the manufacturer. The HeLa cells were seeded in RPMI 1640 medium (with 10% FBS, without phenol red) at the density of 1 x 10⁴ cells/well onto black 96-well

microculture plate. After overnight incubation compound **1** at concentrations IC_{50} and $100 \mu\text{L}$ of 2x Detection Reagent were added. The luminescence and fluorescence ($485\text{nm}_{\text{Ex}}/520\text{--}30\text{nm}_{\text{Em}}$) were measured kinetically over 24 hour time course. The results from three experiments were graphed as net luminescence and net fluorescence signals versus time at a specific compound concentration using GraphPad Prism curve-fit software.

Caspase 3/7 Assay

Caspase 3 and caspase 7 are members of the cysteine aspartic acid-specific protease family that play key effector roles in apoptosis in mammalian cells. The measurement of caspase activity was determined using The Apo-ONE® Homogeneous Caspase-3/7 Assay (Promega). This assay is based on the ability of Caspase-3/7 to cleave the non-fluorescent Caspase Substrate Z-DEVD-R110 to create the fluorescent Rhodamine 110. The HeLa cells were seeded in complete IMDM medium with 10% FBS at the density of 2.5×10^4 cells/well onto black 96-well microculture plate. After overnight incubation the cells were incubated for 6 hours at 37°C , 5% CO_2 with $100 \mu\text{L}$ of compound **1** at concentration $1/2 IC_{50}$, IC_{50} and $2xIC_{50}$. Then $100 \mu\text{L}$ of Apo-ONE Caspase-3/7 Reagent was added to the sample, mixed on plate shaker for one minute and the plate was incubated at dark for 2 hours at room temperature. After incubation the fluorescence was measured at an excitation wavelength of 485 nm and an emission 530 nm. All evaluations were performed in triplicates. An one way ANOVA analysis of variance with a Tukey post hoc was used for multiple comparisons. All statistics were calculated with Prism GraphPad 7 software. A P value of <0.05 was considered significant.

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